

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ROGERS****FIRST NAME: LESLIE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: WPS Office

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following is **not** a category of difference between standard American English and standard British English?
 - Same spelling, same pronunciation.**¹
 - Different pronunciation, same spelling.
 - Different spelling, same pronunciation.
 - Same words, different or additional meanings.
2. Why do researchers use secondary sources in research and essay writing?
 - To acknowledge and respond to the perspectives of other researchers.**²
 - To criticize the points of view of other researchers.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C: Euclid University Press, 2024), 25-26.

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36-37.

- To replicate the researcher's work.
 - Because secondary sources are more reliable than primary research.
3. When should materials from other sources be cited?
- When quoting exact words from a source.**³
 - When using your original ideas.
 - When citing common knowledge.
 - When citing your own personal experiences.
4. Which of the following is **not** a source of potential bias in dissertation research?
- Experience bias.
 - Population bias.
 - Policy bias.
 - Reading bias.**⁴
5. Select the type of measure that is typically used in quantitative research.
- Focus groups.
 - Documents.
 - Unobtrusive observations.**⁵
 - Questions using mainly open-ended items.
6. Which list shows the correct order of dissertation organization?
- _____

³ Ibid., 140.

⁴ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 8-9.

⁵ Ibid., 37.

- Table of Contents, Acknowledgements, List of Tables, List of Figures.
 - Acknowledgements, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures.**⁶
 - Table of Contents, Acknowledgements, List of Figures, List of Tables.
 - Acknowledgments, Table of Contents, List of Figures, List of Tables.
7. Which of the following items should **not** be included in the introduction chapter?
- Recommendations.**⁷
 - Rationale and Significance.
 - Research Questions.
 - Problem Statement.
8. Which research paradigm is referred to as advocacy and focuses on social justice?
- Pragmatism.
 - Social constructivism.
 - Critical Theory.**⁸
 - Postpositivism.
9. Which of the following methods is a systematic inquiry that aims to find effective solutions to complex problems faced in communities?
- Phenomenology.
 - Case study.

⁶ Ibid., 66.

⁷ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 74.

⁸ Ibid., 150.

- Grounded Theory.
- Action Research.**⁹

10. What section of the dissertation outlines the design and manner in which the study was conducted?

- Literature Review.
- Abstract.
- Findings.
- Methodology.**¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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⁹ Ibid., 179.

¹⁰ Ibid., 435.